

Environmental Incentives for Airlines

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Abstract

This paper will investigate whether a connection exists between airlines offering environmental incentives or pollution offset opportunities for their customers and the airlines gaining a larger market share of passengers. That is: do airlines have some incentive to offer pollution offsets or purchase more environmentally friendly aircraft aside from the fuel efficiency which might come with newer aircraft?

1. What Airlines Do

Nearly every major airline has an environmental quota which they have set for themselves above the government requirement. These vary among airlines but are generally focused on decreasing waste produced by the flights (in particular landfill). Looking at a variety of airlines' websites a common trend begins to appear: They eliminated their inflight waste. A select few went further to cut pollution in other ways but many did not, leading to one of the greatest problems with environmental protection: freeriding.

Some airlines are moving towards vertical integration of their business as a means of decreasing their expenses and control a larger portion of markets without directly challenging other airlines with which they might have agreements. In *Consumers' Perception of Airlines* (Kaynak, Kucukemiroglu, & Kara, 1994), the authors discuss this in-depth, relating in particular two

airlines in Australia: the privately owned Ansett, and government run Australian Airlines. The authors explain that “Fearing the consequences of price warfare, [the airlines] competed with each other ... through vertical integration.” This has in some cases resulted in airlines taking environmental cleanliness into their own hands. United Airlines is one such example having made commitments to cut their emissions in half by 2050. Etihad Airlines (a major middle eastern airline) is working on projects to convert municipal waste into jet fuel while China Airlines, among many others, offers passengers the opportunity to purchase carbon offsets for their flights.

Much of what airlines do is in response to new policies enacted by destination airports. Prime examples of this are the London City airport which has very specific traffic patterns, which are the low altitude flight routes that aircraft must follow when near the airport. These particular traffic patterns in London require that aircraft approach the airport at a very steep angle so as to minimize how much they fly over the city due to noise pollution caused by the aircraft. In turn this means that very few aircraft are actually able to fly into the airport due to the flight restrictions, limiting which airlines service London City Airport.

2. The Effect on Consumers

The effect of pollution abatement by airlines is felt by nearly every passenger in one way or another. Airlines eliminate certain service items from their inflight service and replace them with biodegradable options. Airlines also implement drastic decreases in aircraft noise pollution for

both the passengers in the plane and for people on the ground by operating more efficient aircraft.

Airlines increasingly opt for smaller aircraft to fly between major hubs especially when they are relatively near to one another. This is because the demand for flights is usually spread out across the day and given that many of the passengers on these flights are flying for business, they want to minimize travel time. Thus, flying smaller aircraft more frequently offers them both more opportunities to travel and decreased time spent boarding and deplaning on either end of their flights. *The environmental implications of airlines' choice of aircraft* (Givoni & Piet, 2010), details how many major hubs especially in Europe are serviced by smaller aircraft. It states how between “Heathrow and Schiphol alone, there were 26 daily one-way services, and these were offered by an aircraft fleet with an average capacity of 143 seats.” This shift towards narrow body aircraft carrying fewer people may be in an effort to maximize their market share for a specific flight, in addition to having a positive environmental impact. Smaller aircraft are often times more efficient than their larger counterparts given that they are more commonly full when taking off. Furthermore, if they are not sold out, their economic loss to the company is less than the loss due to an equivalent percentage of empty seats on a larger aircraft. If an airline were to choose between a single wide body aircraft servicing two cities once per day versus one smaller aircraft going back and forth three times, they would choose the smaller ones. This is because with smaller aircraft it is far easier to add or eliminate flights on a given route in response to changes in demand. The smaller aircraft allow airlines to scale to the market demand far more

easily than with a larger aircraft which would burn nearly the same amount of fuel whether they have a full passenger load or not.

The major portion of aircraft pollution occurs from jet exhaust which is spewed into the atmosphere and thus this is a very important area of study. Local air pollution or LAP, which is one of the most significant metrics used for measuring aircraft pollution, is measured only by the pollution caused by aircraft below 3000 ft. This in turn makes the smaller aircraft appear more environmentally friendly due to the aircraft burning less fuel. *The environmental implications of airlines' choice of aircraft* (Givoni & Piet, 2010) goes into this subject extensively, detailing the calculations that go into determining the environmental impact of a given flight. Similarly, the smaller the aircraft, the quieter it is (generally), which is often a major problem given noise abatement procedures around airports that aircraft must follow.

Furthermore, the most environmentally conscious travelers will choose to travel by other means such as trains, especially in Europe (Givoni & Piet, 2010). Some airlines are choosing to look for less-polluting aircraft when it comes time to upgrade their fleet however many are being forced to do so given where they fly. These trends towards cleaner aircraft are not due to government fees or mandates but rather by airports requiring them to meet specific noise or pollution abatement minimums. This forces some airlines to stop flying to particular destinations or having to charge much higher fares due to penalties. Higher fares cause travelers to choose alternative airlines for their travel needs, changing their travel behaviors causing a real impact on the environment. *Economic-Environmental trade-off* (Roskopf, Lehner, & Gollnick, 2014), examines this and mentions how in order for airlines to maximize their profit they “want to

demonstrate their environmental commitment to avoid or delay further regulatory action.”

Furthermore the authors detail how “Airlines want to build a greener image with respect to competitors and other forms of transport because they anticipate that this measure could help to attract and retain customers in the future.” While this does highlight the primary question of this paper it does not provide a definitive answer. Nevertheless, if major airlines have business practices which include environmental protection programs then it can be concluded that there must be some economic advantage to doing so. This is further reinforced by the aforementioned fact that many airlines have been actively trying to minimize their in-flight waste and the airlines wanting to remain in profitable markets.

3. The Effect on the Environment

Market Competition and Greening Transportation (Sheu & Li, 2014), analyzes how different pollutants caused by aircraft affect the environment and in which environments they are most damaging. They detail how aircraft will affect one of the most common metrics for pollution which is parts per million (ppm) of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere. The paper remarks on how predictions by the IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change) show that CO₂ emissions caused by aircraft may increase by as much as 15% by 2050 due to air travel becoming more affordable. They and many others have urged industry leaders to look for new technologies to help offset the inevitable increase in carbon emissions, noting “Future growth of the aviation

industry will likely be accompanied by increases in carbon emissions unless significant efficiency improvements and mitigating measures are implemented.”

When looking at the economic effects on airlines, we see the results of some possible legislative programs, which are consistently shot down by lobbyists. Airlines would receive a 3% loss in economic benefit to achieve a 6% improvement in their environmental goal according to *Economic-environmental trade-offs* (Roskopf, Lehner, & Gollnick, 2014). This means that in order for the government to incentivize this type of environmental improvement they would have to either subsidize at least 3% to cover the airline’s economic loss or tax at least 3% if they chose not to implement environmental improvements. This raises a significant counterpoint to what was mentioned earlier in the same paper (see section 2 on airlines’ choices to go greener) where airlines would not willingly sacrifice economic performance for environmental performance currently but “In the future, growing pressure from customers and society might change this attitude.”

There are, however, some costs that all airlines will incur if they fly to particular regions of the world. In the EU, environmental restrictions require that “all airlines flying in and out of EU airports [must have] carbon permits (CPs) starting in January 2012” according to *Market Competition and Greening Transportation* (Sheu & Li, 2014). The idea with this is that for airlines to fly into particular airports they must possess specific certifications of environmental efficiency based on their pollution. It is further a cap and trade system to help minimize pollution in some high-density environments. Depending on the airport and the aircraft in an airline’s fleet,

they may or may not be allowed to travel to a given destination. This provides a strong economic incentive to invest in cleaner planes and or practices to ensure there is no loss of market.

4. Discussion

When trying to analyze the different articles and conduct research myself it was challenging to distinguish what might have caused changes in consumers' tendencies from one airline to another. This was in part due to many airlines having had negative public relations issues in the last few years. Given that there are so many issues with trying to determine trends in consumer preferences without conducting large costly research projects, it is difficult to find research done on this topic. Furthermore, it was mentioned that it would be near impossible to conduct such projects due to rapidly changing markets. This is because they would have to span multiple years and during that time airlines change their policies or new more efficient technologies arise which introduces new variables completely throwing off the initial data.

That being said, the connection between airlines which practice more environmentally friendly operations and their controlling a larger market share is somewhat clearer than might have been expected. This is not always by passengers' conscious decisions to choose one airline over another but rather that airports and other systems make the decision for them. There are cases where a traveler might choose one airline over a different one, if their prices are nearly the same, based on their inflight environmental practices as mentioned in the second section, however ease of use of an airline often trumps that decision especially for business travelers. This coupled with

the requirements which certain airports enact on aircraft flying into the airport, limits which airlines can fly to a given destination often based on some environmental qualifications.

In looking at the original question of this paper, we can conclude that there is no clear correlation between airlines with more environmentally friendly practices and more passengers choosing that airline. Most policies which airlines implement are not for the primary purpose of environmental protection but rather for their economic profitability.